

RT² Profiler PCR Array Gene Expression Analysis Report

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Introduction

Cataloged arrays

RT² Profiler PCR Arrays are highly reliable and sensitive gene expression profiling tools for analyzing focused panels of genes in signal transduction, biological processes or disease research pathways using real-time PCR. Each cataloged RT² Profiler PCR Array contains a list of the pathway-focused genes as well as five housekeeping (reference) genes on the array. In addition, each array contains a panel of proprietary controls to monitor genomic DNA contamination (GDC) as well as the first strand synthesis (RTC) and real-time PCR efficiency (PPC). The qPCR Assays used in PCR Arrays are laboratory-verified and optimized to work under standard conditions enabling a large number of genes to be assayed simultaneously. Their specificity is guaranteed when RT² SYBR Green qPCR Master Mixes are used as part of the complete PCR Array System protocol.

In this study, 96 genes were profiled on 16 samples with the PAHS-024Z.

Summary and workflow

Cataloged arrays

1. Mature RNA was isolated using an RNA extraction kit according to the manufacturer's instructions.
2. RNA quality was determined using a spectrophotometer and was reverse transcribed using a cDNA conversion kit.
3. The cDNA was used on the real-time RT² Profiler PCR Array (QIAGEN, Cat. no. PAHS-024Z) in combination with RT² SYBR® Green qPCR Mastermix (Cat. no. 330529).

C_T values were exported to an Excel file to create a table of C_T values. This table was then uploaded on to the data analysis web portal at <http://www.qiagen.com/geneglobe>. Samples were assigned to controls and test groups. C_T values were normalized based on a/an Manual Selection of reference genes.

The data analysis web portal calculates fold change/regulation using delta delta C_T method, in which delta C_T is calculated between gene of interest (GOI) and an average of reference genes (HKG), followed by delta-delta C_T calculations (delta C_T (Test Group)-delta C_T (Control Group)). Fold Change is then calculated using $2^{-\Delta\Delta C_T}$ formula. The data analysis web portal also plots scatter plot, volcano plot, clustergram, and heat map.

This data analysis report was exported from the QIAGEN web portal at GeneGlobe.

Gene Table

Position	RefSeq Number	Symbol	Description
A01	NM_005163	AKT1	V-akt murine thymoma viral oncogene homolog 1
A02	NM_001145	ANG	Angiogenin, ribonuclease, RNase A family, 5
A03	NM_001146	ANGPT1	Angiopoietin 1
A04	NM_001147	ANGPT2	Angiopoietin 2
A05	NM_001039667	ANGPTL4	Angiopoietin-like 4
A06	NM_001150	ANPEP	Alanyl (membrane) aminopeptidase
A07	NM_001702	ADGRB1	Brain-specific angiogenesis inhibitor 1
A08	NM_002986	CCL11	Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 11
A09	NM_002982	CCL2	Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 2
A10	NM_001795	CDH5	Cadherin 5, type 2 (vascular endothelium)
A11	NM_030582	COL18A1	Collagen, type XVIII, alpha 1
A12	NM_000091	COL4A3	Collagen, type IV, alpha 3 (Goodpasture antigen)
B01	NM_001901	CTGF	Connective tissue growth factor
B02	NM_001511	CXCL1	Chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 1 (melanoma growth stimulating activity, alpha)
B03	NM_001565	CXCL10	Chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 10
B04	NM_002994	CXCL5	Chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 5
B05	NM_002993	CXCL6	Chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 6 (granulocyte chemotactic protein 2)
B06	NM_002416	CXCL9	Chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 9
B07	NM_001955	EDN1	Endothelin 1
B08	NM_182685	EFNA1	Ephrin-A1
B09	NM_004093	EFNB2	Ephrin-B2
B10	NM_001963	EGF	Epidermal growth factor
B11	NM_000118	ENG	Endoglin
B12	NM_004444	EPHB4	EPH receptor B4
C01	NM_004448	ERBB2	V-erb-b2 erythroblastic leukemia viral oncogene homolog 2, neuro/glioblastoma derived oncogene homolog (avian)
C02	NM_001993	F3	Coagulation factor III (thromboplastin, tissue factor)
C03	NM_000800	FGF1	Fibroblast growth factor 1 (acidic)
C04	NM_002006	FGF2	Fibroblast growth factor 2 (basic)
C05	NM_000142	FGFR3	Fibroblast growth factor receptor 3
C06	NM_004469	FIGF	C-fos induced growth factor (vascular endothelial growth factor D)
C07	NM_002019	FLT1	Fms-related tyrosine kinase 1 (vascular endothelial growth factor/vascular permeability factor receptor)
C08	NM_002026	FN1	Fibronectin 1
C09	NM_000601	HGF	Hepatocyte growth factor (hepapoietin A; scatter factor)
C10	NM_001530	HIF1A	Hypoxia inducible factor 1, alpha subunit (basic helix-loop-helix transcription factor)

Position	RefSeq Number	Symbol	Description
C11	NM_006665	HPSE	Heparanase
C12	NM_002165	ID1	Inhibitor of DNA binding 1, dominant negative helix-loop-helix protein
D01	NM_024013	IFNA1	Interferon, alpha 1
D02	NM_000619	IFNG	Interferon, gamma
D03	NM_000618	IGF1	Insulin-like growth factor 1 (somatomedin C)
D04	NM_000576	IL1B	Interleukin 1, beta
D05	NM_000600	IL6	Interleukin 6 (interferon, beta 2)
D06	NM_000584	CXCL8	Interleukin 8
D07	NM_002210	ITGAV	Integrin, alpha V (vitronectin receptor, alpha polypeptide, antigen CD51)
D08	NM_000212	ITGB3	Integrin, beta 3 (platelet glycoprotein IIIa, antigen CD61)
D09	NM_000214	JAG1	Jagged 1
D10	NM_002253	KDR	Kinase insert domain receptor (a type III receptor tyrosine kinase)
D11	NM_007015	LECT1	Leukocyte cell derived chemotaxin 1
D12	NM_000230	LEP	Leptin
E01	NM_002391	MDK	Midkine (neurite growth-promoting factor 2)
E02	NM_004995	MMP14	Matrix metalloproteinase 14 (membrane-inserted)
E03	NM_004530	MMP2	Matrix metalloproteinase 2 (gelatinase A, 72kDa gelatinase, 72kDa type IV collagenase)
E04	NM_004994	MMP9	Matrix metalloproteinase 9 (gelatinase B, 92kDa gelatinase, 92kDa type IV collagenase)
E05	NM_000603	NOS3	Nitric oxide synthase 3 (endothelial cell)
E06	NM_004557	NOTCH4	Notch 4
E07	NM_003873	NRP1	Neuropilin 1
E08	NM_003872	NRP2	Neuropilin 2
E09	NM_002607	PDGFA	Platelet-derived growth factor alpha polypeptide
E10	NM_000442	PECAM1	Platelet/endothelial cell adhesion molecule
E11	NM_002619	PF4	Platelet factor 4
E12	NM_002632	PGF	Placental growth factor
F01	NM_002658	PLAU	Plasminogen activator, urokinase
F02	NM_000301	PLG	Plasminogen
F03	NM_021935	PROK2	Prokineticin 2
F04	NM_000962	PTGS1	Prostaglandin-endoperoxide synthase 1 (prostaglandin G/H synthase and cyclooxygenase)
F05	NM_001400	S1PR1	Sphingosine-1-phosphate receptor 1
F06	NM_000602	SERPINE1	Serpin peptidase inhibitor, clade E (nexin, plasminogen activator inhibitor type 1), member 1
F07	NM_002615	SERPINF1	Serpin peptidase inhibitor, clade F (alpha-2 antiplasmin, pigment epithelium derived factor), member 1
F08	NM_021972	SPHK1	Sphingosine kinase 1
F09	NM_000459	TEK	TEK tyrosine kinase, endothelial
F10	NM_003236	TGFA	Transforming growth factor, alpha
F11	NM_000660	TGFB1	Transforming growth factor, beta 1

Position	RefSeq Number	Symbol	Description
F12	NM_003238	TGFB2	Transforming growth factor, beta 2
G01	NM_004612	TGFBR1	Transforming growth factor, beta receptor 1
G02	NM_003246	THBS1	Thrombospondin 1
G03	NM_003247	THBS2	Thrombospondin 2
G04	NM_005424	TIE1	Tyrosine kinase with immunoglobulin-like and EGF-like domains 1
G05	NM_003254	TIMP1	TIMP metalloproteinase inhibitor 1
G06	NM_003255	TIMP2	TIMP metalloproteinase inhibitor 2
G07	NM_000362	TIMP3	TIMP metalloproteinase inhibitor 3
G08	NM_000594	TNF	Tumor necrosis factor
G09	NM_001953	TYMP	Thymidine phosphorylase
G10	NM_003376	VEGFA	Vascular endothelial growth factor A
G11	NM_003377	VEGFB	Vascular endothelial growth factor B
G12	NM_005429	VEGFC	Vascular endothelial growth factor C
H01	NM_001101	ACTB	Actin, beta
H02	NM_004048	B2M	Beta-2-microglobulin
H03	NM_002046	GAPDH	Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase
H04	NM_000194	HPRT1	Hypoxanthine phosphoribosyltransferase 1
H05	NM_001002	RPLP0	Ribosomal protein, large, P0
H06	SA_00105	HGDC	Human Genomic DNA Contamination
H07	SA_00104	RTC	Reverse Transcription Control
H08	SA_00104	RTC	Reverse Transcription Control
H09	SA_00104	RTC	Reverse Transcription Control
H10	SA_00103	PPC	Positive PCR Control
H11	SA_00103	PPC	Positive PCR Control
H12	SA_00103	PPC	Positive PCR Control

Data analysis setup

Sample management

Sample ID	Sample Name	Group
1	NG	Control Group
2	NG.1	Control Group
3	NG.2	Control Group
4	NG.3	Control Group
5	HG	Group 1
6	HG.1	Group 1
7	HG.2	Group 1
8	HG.3	Group 1
9	HG + RVX208	Group 2
10	HG + RVX208.1	Group 2
11	HG + RVX208.2	Group 2
12	HG + RVX208.3	Group 2
13	HG + DMSO	Group 3
14	HG + DMSO.1	Group 3
15	HG + DMSO.2	Group 3
16	HG + DMSO.3	Group 3

Pre-amplification

A pre-amplification using the appropriate species- and pathway-specific RT² PreAMP Primer Mix was performed and the appropriate corrections were made during the data analysis procedure.

Lower limit of detection

The C_T cut-off was set to 35

Data quality control (QC)

Quality checks performed and results

Test Performed	Test Result
1. PCR Array Reproducibility	All Samples Passed
2. Reverse Transcription Efficiency	All Samples Passed
3. Genomic DNA Contamination	All Samples Passed

Normalization analysis

Manual Selection

Groups	Samples	ACTB	B2M	GAPDH	HPRT1	RPLP0	Arithmetic Mean	Average Arithmetic Mean
Control Group	NG	18.79	21.86	19.84	26.63	19.43	21.31	20.90
Control Group	NG.1	18.57	21.65	19.61	26.39	19.09	21.06	
Control Group	NG.2	19.93	19.93	19.93	19.93	19.93	19.93	
Control Group	NG.3	18.79	21.86	19.84	26.63	19.43	21.31	
Group 1	HG	18.65	21.61	19.69	26.51	19.42	21.18	20.56
Group 1	HG.1	19.95	19.95	19.95	19.95	19.95	19.95	
Group 1	HG.2	19.95	19.95	19.95	19.95	19.95	19.95	
Group 1	HG.3	18.65	21.61	19.69	26.51	19.42	21.18	
Group 2	HG + RVX208	20.35	22.10	20.98	27.51	19.98	22.18	21.79
Group 2	HG + RVX208.1	21.40	21.40	21.40	21.40	21.40	21.40	
Group 2	HG + RVX208.2	21.40	21.40	21.40	21.40	21.40	21.40	
Group 2	HG + RVX208.3	20.35	22.10	20.98	27.51	19.98	22.18	
Group 3	HG + DMSO	19.12	21.71	20.06	26.54	19.85	21.45	21.06
Group 3	HG + DMSO.1	20.67	20.67	20.67	20.67	20.67	20.67	
Group 3	HG + DMSO.2	20.67	20.67	20.67	20.67	20.67	20.67	
Group 3	HG + DMSO.3	19.12	21.71	20.06	26.54	19.85	21.45	

In the Manual Selection method, the arithmetic or geometric means of the data from the assays for the housekeeping / reference genes listed in the table were used to normalize the raw data.

Result

Fold regulation and p-value

Test Group	Control Group	Fold Regulation Threshold	p-Value Threshold
Group 1	Control Group	2	0.05

Position	Gene Symbol	Fold Regulation	p-Value	Comments
D04	IL1B	3.98	0.037226	
D05	IL6	10.30	0.005766	A
D06	CXCL8	2.15	0.000000	
G02	THBS1	7.11	0.000008	
G03	THBS2	2.39	0.000102	
B06	CXCL9	-3.98	0.022280	
G10	VEGFA	-6.65	0.015561	

Fold-Change ($2^{(-\Delta\Delta C_t)}$) is the normalized gene expression ($2^{(-\Delta C_t)}$) in the Test Sample divided the normalized gene expression ($2^{(-\Delta C_t)}$) in the Control Sample. Fold-Regulation represents fold-change results in a biologically meaningful way. Fold-change values greater than one indicates a positive- or an up-regulation, and the fold-regulation is equal to the fold-change. Fold-change values less than one indicate a negative or down-regulation, and the fold-regulation is the negative inverse of the fold-change.

The p values are calculated based on a Student's t-test of the replicate $2^{(-\Delta C_t)}$ values for each gene in the control group and treatment groups, and p values less than 0.05 are indicated in red. The p-value calculation used is based on parametric, unpaired, two-sample equal variance, two-tailed distribution – a method widely accepted in scientific literature.

Scatter Plot

Test Group	Control Group	Fold Regulation Threshold
Group 1	Control Group	2

The Scatter Plot compares the normalized expression of every gene on the PCR Array between the two selected groups by plotting them against one another to quickly visualize large gene expression changes. The center diagonal line indicates unchanged gene expression, while the outer diagonal lines indicate the selected fold regulation threshold. Genes with data points beyond the outer lines in the upper left and lower right corners are up-regulated or down-regulated, respectively, by more than the fold regulation threshold in the y-axis Group relative to the x-axis Group.

Genes Over-Expressed in Group 1 vs. Control Group

Position	Gene Symbol	Fold Regulation	Comments	RT ² qPCR Assay Catalog #
D04	IL1B	3.98		PPH00171C
D05	IL6	10.30	A	PPH00560C
D06	CXCL8	2.15		PPH00568A
E04	MMP9	2.94	B	PPH00152E
G02	THBS1	7.11		PPH00799F
G03	THBS2	2.39		PPH00238F
H04	HPRT1	2.50		PPH01018C

Genes Under-Expressed in Group 1 vs. Control Group

Position	Gene Symbol	Fold Regulation	Comments	RT ² qPCR Assay Catalog #
A03	ANGPT1	-2.62	B	PPH00374B
A12	COL4A3	-4.53	B	PPH02131C
B06	CXCL9	-3.98		PPH00700B
B10	EGF	-2.76	B	PPH00137B
C05	FGFR3	-2.19	B	PPH00382A
C09	HGF	-3.24	B	PPH00163C
D02	IFNG	-3.27	B	PPH00380C
D11	LECT1	-2.41	B	PPH19892A
F03	PROK2	-183.49	A	PPH24188A
G07	TIMP3	-2.34	B	PPH00762B
G10	VEGFA	-6.65		PPH00251C
G11	VEGFB	-2.14		PPH00671B

Volcano Plot

Test Group	Control Group	Fold Regulation Threshold	p-Value Threshold
Group 1	Control Group	2	0.05

Group 1 vs. Control Group

The Volcano Plot identifies significant gene expression changes by plotting the log₂ of the fold changes in gene expression on the x-axis versus their statistical significance on the y-axis. The center vertical line indicates unchanged gene expression, while the two outer vertical lines indicate the selected fold regulation threshold. The horizontal line indicates the selected p-value threshold. Genes with data points in the far upper left (down-regulated) and far upper right (up-regulated) sections meet the selected fold regulation and p-value thresholds. By combining the fold change results with the p-value statistical test results, genes with both large and small expression changes that are statistically significant are easily visualized.

Genes Over-Expressed in Group 1 vs. Control Group

Position	Gene Symbol	Fold Regulation	p-Value	Comments	RT ² qPCR Assay Catalog #
D04	IL1B	3.98	0.037226		PPH00171C
D05	IL6	10.30	0.005766	A	PPH00560C
D06	CXCL8	2.15	0.000000		PPH00568A
E04	MMP9	2.94	0.158274	B	PPH00152E
G02	THBS1	7.11	0.000008		PPH00799F
G03	THBS2	2.39	0.000102		PPH00238F
H04	HPRT1	2.50	0.537174		PPH01018C

Genes Under-Expressed in Group 1 vs. Control Group

Position	Gene Symbol	Fold Regulation	p-Value	Comments	RT ² qPCR Assay Catalog #
A03	ANGPT1	-2.62	0.061991	B	PPH00374B
A12	COL4A3	-4.53	0.110122	B	PPH02131C
B06	CXCL9	-3.98	0.022280		PPH00700B
B10	EGF	-2.76	0.294390	B	PPH00137B
C05	FGFR3	-2.19	0.088571	B	PPH00382A
C09	HGF	-3.24	0.284058	B	PPH00163C
D02	IFNG	-3.27	0.311642	B	PPH00380C
D11	LECT1	-2.41	0.055993	B	PPH19892A
F03	PROK2	-183.49	0.355918	A	PPH24188A
G07	TIMP3	-2.34	0.182593	B	PPH00762B
G10	VEGFA	-6.65	0.015561		PPH00251C
G11	VEGFB	-2.14	0.131823		PPH00671B

Clustergram

Sample	Dimension	Join Type	Color Coded
Array	2-D	Average	Genes

Heat Map

Test Group	Control Group
Group 1	Control Group

Visualization of log₂(Fold Change)

Layout	01	02	03	04	05	06	07	08	09	10	11	12
A	AKT1 / -1.14	ANG / 1.07	ANGPT1 / -2.62 / B	ANGPT2 / -1.65	ANGPTL4 / 1.07	ANPEP / -1.04	ADGRB1 / -1.98 / B	CCL11 / -1.36 / B	CCL2 / 1.83	CDH5 / -1.19	COL18A1 / -1.67	COL4A3 / -4.53 / B
B	CTGF / -1.04	CXCL1 / 1.27	CXCL10 / -1.92 / B	CXCL5 / -1.16 / B	CXCL6 / 1.81	CXCL9 / -3.98	EDN1 / 1.02	EFNA1 / -1.39	EFNB2 / -1.37	EGF / -2.76 / B	ENG / -1.07	EPHB4 / -1.22
C	ERBB2 / -1.45	F3 / -1.25 / B	FGF1 / -1.74 / B	FGF2 / -1.01	FGFR3 / -2.19 / B	FIGF / -1.0 / B	FLT1 / -1.07	FN1 / -1.16	HGF / -3.24 / B	HIF1A / 1.11	HPSE / 1.05	ID1 / 1.08
D	IFNA1 / -1.1 / B	IFNG / -3.27 / B	IGF1 / 1.02 / B	IL1B / 3.98	IL6 / 10.3 / A	CXCL8 / 2.15	ITGAV / 1.12	ITGB3 / 1.19	JAG1 / 1.01	KDR / -1.14	LECT1 / -2.41 / B	LEP / -1.42
E	MDK / -1.16	MMP14 / -1.41	MMP2 / -1.2	MMP9 / 2.94 / B	NOS3 / -1.23	NOTCH4 / -1.03	NRP1 / -1.2	NRP2 / -1.22	PDGFA / -1.1	PECAM1 / -1.01	PF4 / -1.25 / B	PGF / -1.53
F	PLAU / 1.03	PLG / -1.33 / B	PROK2 / -183.49 / A	PTGS1 / -1.07	S1PR1 / 1.08	SERPINE1 / 1.1	SERPINF1 / -1.19	SPHK1 / -1.24	TEK / -1.0	TGFA / -1.6	TGFB1 / -1.06	TGFB2 / 1.29
G	TGFB1 / -1.21	THBS1 / 7.11	THBS2 / 2.39	TIE1 / -1.23	TIMP1 / -1.14	TIMP2 / 1.07	TIMP3 / -2.34 / B	TNF / -1.11 / B	TYMP / -1.08 / B	VEGFA / -6.65	VEGFB / -2.14	VEGFC / 1.58

What's next

Thank you for using the RT² Profiler Data Analysis Software.

The Data Analysis software delivers a list of expression changes in the samples from the supplied data. However, this result often only starts an investigation into the underlying mechanisms at work. In order to assist in further analysis, the QIAGEN now utilizes the latest bioinformatics tools to analyze the data and suggest regulatory mechanisms and future experiments. Please review the results from the selected tools below.

Gene Expression: This tool will help define a panel of genes based of this experiment's results. This panel may represent a putative biomarker set, a target gene set or simply a collection of genes. The tool is designed to deliver a list of gene expression assays that would allow the user to follow-up the results of the analyzed experiment.

miRNA Regulation: This tool will identify candidate miRNA regulators in your experimental system. The tool is designed to deliver a list of miRNAs that could be targeting the genes that had observed changes in expression in your selected samples.

DNA Methylation: This tool will help define a panel of differentially expressed genes based on this experiment's results. Altered methylation patterns on the genes' promoters may be responsible for these gene expression changes. This tool is designed to deliver a list of available DNA methylation assays for those differentially expressed genes that would allow the user to follow-up their gene expression experiment with an epigenetic analysis.

Transcription Factor / Histone: This tool will help define a panel of differentially expressed genes based on this experiment's results. Altered transcription factor binding activity on the genes' promoters may be responsible for these gene expression changes. Altered histone modification patterns on the genes' promoters may also be responsible for these gene expression changes. This tool is designed to deliver a list of the transcription factors that might regulate the selected differentially expressed genes as well as the available respective gene-specific real-time PCR assays for DNA from anti-transcription factor or anti-histone chromatin immunoprecipitations. These assays would then allow the user to follow-up their gene expression experiment with an epigenetic analysis.

Protein Detection: This tool will help define a panel of cytokines or chemokines based on this experiment's results. This panel may represent a putative biomarker set, a target gene set or simply a collection of genes. The tool is designed to deliver a list of ELISAs that would allow the user to follow-up the results of the analyzed experiment.

Somatic Mutation: This tool will help define a panel of genes based on this experiment's results. Mutations in these genes may affect whether their expression changes have any effect or different effects on the experimental model system. The tool is designed to deliver a list of available somatic mutation assays for these differentially expressed genes that would allow the user to follow-up the results of the analyzed experiment.

Gene Expression, DNA Methylation, Protein Detection, Somatic Mutation

Test Group	Control Group	Fold Regulation Threshold	p-Value Threshold
Group 1	Control Group	2	0.05

Position	Symbol	Fold Regulation	p-Value	RT2 qPCR Assay	EpiTect Methyl II qPCR Assay	Single Analyte ELISArray	Somatic Mutation Assay
D04	IL1B	3.98	0.037226	PPH00171C		SEH00171A	
D05	IL6	10.3	0.005766	PPH00560C		SEH00560A	
D06	CXCL8	2.15	0.0	PPH00568A			
G02	THBS1	7.11	8e-06	PPH00799F	EPHS104439-1A		
G03	THBS2	2.39	0.000102	PPH00238F			
B06	CXCL9	-3.98	0.02228	PPH00700B		SEH00700A	
G10	VEGFA	-6.65	0.015561	PPH00251C	EPHS112506-1A		

miRNA Regulation

Test Group	Control Group	Fold Regulation Threshold	p-Value Threshold
Group 1	Control Group	2	0.05

Genes Under-Expressed in Group 1 vs. Control Group

Position	Gene Symbol	Fold Regulation	p-Value
B06	CXCL9	-3.98	0.022280
G10	VEGFA	-6.65	0.015561

miRNA Regulating Genes Under-Expressed in Group 1 vs. Control Group

miRNA Name	Strongest Strength Score	miScript Assay	miScript Mimic	miScript Inhibitor	Targeted Genes
hsa-miR-1	-0.12	MS00008358	MSY0000416	MIN0000416	VEGFA
hsa-miR-106a-5p	-0.11	MS00029274	MSY0000103	MIN0000103	VEGFA
hsa-miR-106b-5p	-0.13	MS00003402	MSY0000680	MIN0000680	VEGFA
hsa-miR-140-5p	-0.24	MS00003500	MSY0000431	MIN0000431	VEGFA
hsa-miR-15a-5p	-0.43	MS00003178	MSY0000068	MIN0000068	VEGFA
hsa-miR-15b-5p	-0.43	MS00008792	MSY0000417	MIN0000417	VEGFA
hsa-miR-16-5p	-0.44	MS00031493	MSY0000069	MIN0000069	VEGFA
hsa-miR-17-5p	-0.11	MS00029274	MSY0000070	MIN0000070	VEGFA
hsa-miR-1825	-0.12	MS00014672	MSY0006765	MIN0006765	VEGFA
hsa-miR-185-5p	-0.33	MS00003647	MSY0000455	MIN0000455	VEGFA
hsa-miR-186-5p	-0.41	MS00003654	MSY0000456	MIN0000456	VEGFA
hsa-miR-195-5p	-0.44	MS00003703	MSY0000461	MIN0000461	VEGFA
hsa-miR-199a-5p	-0.15	MS00006741	MSY0000231	MIN0000231	VEGFA
hsa-miR-199b-5p	-0.15	MS00003731	MSY0000263	MIN0000263	VEGFA
hsa-miR-200b-3p	-0.27	MS00009016	MSY0000318	MIN0000318	VEGFA
hsa-miR-200c-3p	-0.27	MS00003752	MSY0000617	MIN0000617	VEGFA
hsa-miR-203a	-0.20	MS00003766	MSY0000264	MIN0000264	VEGFA
hsa-miR-205-5p	-0.40	MS00003780	MSY0000266	MIN0000266	VEGFA
hsa-miR-206	-0.12	MS00003787	MSY0000462	MIN0000462	VEGFA
hsa-miR-20a-5p	-0.11	MS00003199	MSY0000075	MIN0000075	VEGFA
hsa-miR-20b-5p	-0.11	MS00003206	MSY0001413	MIN0001413	VEGFA
hsa-miR-299-3p	-0.39	MS00031682	MSY0000687	MIN0000687	VEGFA
hsa-miR-29a-3p	-0.53	MS00003262	MSY0000086	MIN0000086	VEGFA
hsa-miR-29b-3p	-0.53	MS00006566	MSY0000100	MIN0000100	VEGFA
hsa-miR-29c-3p	-0.53	MS00003269	MSY0000681	MIN0000681	VEGFA
hsa-miR-302a-3p	-0.06	MS00009331	MSY0000684	MIN0000684	VEGFA
hsa-miR-302b-3p	-0.06	MS00003906	MSY0000715	MIN0000715	VEGFA

miRNA Name	Strongest Strength Score	miScript Assay	miScript Mimic	miScript Inhibitor	Targeted Genes
hsa-miR-302c-3p	-0.06	MS00003913	MSY0000717	MIN0000717	VEGFA
hsa-miR-302d-3p	-0.07	MS00003920	MSY0000718	MIN0000718	VEGFA
hsa-miR-302e	-0.09	MS00014693	MSY0005931	MIN0005931	VEGFA
hsa-miR-361-5p	-0.49	MS00004032	MSY0000703	MIN0000703	VEGFA
hsa-miR-372-3p	-0.07	MS00004067	MSY0000724	MIN0000724	VEGFA
hsa-miR-373-3p	-0.04	MS00031815	MSY0000726	MIN0000726	VEGFA
hsa-miR-377-3p	-0.11	MS00004095	MSY0000730	MIN0000730	VEGFA
hsa-miR-383-5p	-0.24	MS00004130	MSY0000738	MIN0000738	VEGFA
hsa-miR-410-3p	-0.08	MS00004144	MSY0002171	MIN0002171	VEGFA
hsa-miR-424-5p	-0.43	MS00004186	MSY0001341	MIN0001341	VEGFA
hsa-miR-429	-0.33	MS00004193	MSY0001536	MIN0001536	VEGFA
hsa-miR-452-5p	-0.31	MS00031871	MSY0001635	MIN0001635	VEGFA
hsa-miR-497-5p	-0.43	MS00004361	MSY0002820	MIN0002820	VEGFA
hsa-miR-503-5p	-0.15	MS00033838	MSY0002874	MIN0002874	VEGFA
hsa-miR-519d-3p	-0.11	MS00004508	MSY0002853	MIN0002853	VEGFA
hsa-miR-520a-3p	-0.04	MS00004522	MSY0002834	MIN0002834	VEGFA
hsa-miR-520b	-0.09	MS00033859	MSY0002843	MIN0002843	VEGFA
hsa-miR-520c-3p	-0.09	MS00007413	MSY0002846	MIN0002846	VEGFA
hsa-miR-520d-3p	-0.04	MS00004529	MSY0002856	MIN0002856	VEGFA
hsa-miR-520e	-0.06	MS00004536	MSY0002825	MIN0002825	VEGFA
hsa-miR-520g-3p	-0.08	MS00031955	MSY0002858	MIN0002858	VEGFA
hsa-miR-520h	-0.08	MS00044926	MSY0002867	MIN0002867	VEGFA
hsa-miR-543	-0.13	MS00010080	MSY0004954	MIN0004954	VEGFA
hsa-miR-548a-3p	-0.18	MS00033887	MSY0003251	MIN0003251	VEGFA
hsa-miR-548c-3p	-0.24	MS00010122	MSY0003285	MIN0003285	VEGFA
hsa-miR-548d-3p	-0.27	MS00007161	MSY0003323	MIN0003323	VEGFA
hsa-miR-548e-3p	-0.21	MS00014735	MSY0005874	MIN0005874	VEGFA
hsa-miR-548f-3p	-0.18	MS00014742	MSY0005895	MIN0005895	VEGFA
hsa-miR-548p	-0.39	MS00042413	MSY0005934	MIN0005934	VEGFA
hsa-miR-556-3p	-0.14	MS00032004	MSY0004793	MIN0004793	VEGFA
hsa-miR-569	-0.13	MS00010206	MSY0003234	MIN0003234	VEGFA
hsa-miR-576-5p	-0.46	MS00007798	MSY0003241	MIN0003241	VEGFA
hsa-miR-578	-0.52	MS00004816	MSY0003243	MIN0003243	VEGFA
hsa-miR-579-3p	-0.09	MS00007805	MSY0003244	MIN0003244	VEGFA
hsa-miR-613	-0.15	MS00005054	MSY0003281	MIN0003281	VEGFA
hsa-miR-646	-0.13	MS00032074	MSY0003316	MIN0003316	VEGFA
hsa-miR-655-3p	-0.52	MS00010472	MSY0003331	MIN0003331	VEGFA

miRNA Name	Strongest Strength Score	miScript Assay	miScript Mimic	miScript Inhibitor	Targeted Genes
hsa-miR-889-3p	-0.44	MS00010710	MSY0004921	MIN0004921	VEGFA
hsa-miR-93-5p	-0.11	MS00003346	MSY0000093	MIN0000093	VEGFA
hsa-miR-944	-0.19	MS00010899	MSY0004987	MIN0004987	VEGFA

Genes Over-Expressed in Group 1 vs. Control Group

Position	Gene Symbol	Fold Regulation	p-Value
D04	IL1B	3.98	0.037226
D05	IL6	10.30	0.005766
D06	CXCL8	2.15	0.000000
G02	THBS1	7.11	0.000008
G03	THBS2	2.39	0.000102

miRNA Regulating Genes Over-Expressed in Group 1 vs. Control Group

miRNA Name	Strongest Strength Score	miScript Assay	miScript Mimic	miScript Inhibitor	Targeted Genes
hsa-let-7a-5p	-0.24	MS00031220	MSY0000062	MIN0000062	THBS1
hsa-let-7b-5p	-0.22	MS00003122	MSY0000063	MIN0000063	THBS1
hsa-let-7c-5p	-0.25	MS00003129	MSY0000064	MIN0000064	THBS1
hsa-let-7d-5p	-0.20	MS00003136	MSY0000065	MIN0000065	THBS1
hsa-let-7e-5p	-0.24	MS00031227	MSY0000066	MIN0000066	THBS1
hsa-let-7f-5p	-0.24	MS00006489	MSY0000067	MIN0000067	THBS1
hsa-let-7g-5p	-0.24	MS00008337	MSY0000414	MIN0000414	THBS1
hsa-let-7i-5p	-0.23	MS00003157	MSY0000415	MIN0000415	THBS1
hsa-miR-1	-0.28	MS00008358	MSY0000416	MIN0000416	THBS1
hsa-miR-101-3p	-0.14	MS00008372	MSY0000099	MIN0000099	THBS1
hsa-miR-124-3p	-0.20	MS00006622	MSY0000422	MIN0000422	THBS2
hsa-miR-1271-5p	-0.16	MS00014399	MSY0005796	MIN0005796	THBS2
hsa-miR-139-5p	-0.23	MS00003493	MSY0000250	MIN0000250	THBS1
hsa-miR-144-3p	-0.12	MS00020328	MSY0000436	MIN0000436	THBS1
hsa-miR-182-5p	-0.45	MS00008855	MSY0000259	MIN0000259	THBS2
hsa-miR-1827	-0.32	MS00014686	MSY0006767	MIN0006767	THBS1
hsa-miR-194-5p	-0.38	MS00006727	MSY0000460	MIN0000460	THBS1
hsa-miR-19a-3p	-0.43	MS00003192	MSY0000073	MIN0000073	THBS1
hsa-miR-19b-3p	-0.43	MS00031584	MSY0000074	MIN0000074	THBS1
hsa-miR-202-3p	-0.20	MS00009037	MSY0002811	MIN0002811	THBS1
hsa-miR-206	-0.28	MS00003787	MSY0000462	MIN0000462	THBS1
hsa-miR-221-3p	-0.21	MS00003857	MSY0000278	MIN0000278	THBS1
hsa-miR-222-3p	-0.21	MS00007609	MSY0000279	MIN0000279	THBS1
hsa-miR-30a-5p	-0.21	MS00007350	MSY0000087	MIN0000087	THBS2
hsa-miR-30b-5p	-0.21	MS00003276	MSY0000420	MIN0000420	THBS2
hsa-miR-30c-5p	-0.21	MS00009366	MSY0000244	MIN0000244	THBS2
hsa-miR-30d-5p	-0.21	MS00009387	MSY0000245	MIN0000245	THBS2
hsa-miR-30e-5p	-0.21	MS00009401	MSY0000692	MIN0000692	THBS2

miRNA Name	Strongest Strength Score	miScript Assay	miScript Mimic	miScript Inhibitor	Targeted Genes
hsa-miR-377-3p	-0.23	MS00004095	MSY0000730	MIN0000730	THBS1
hsa-miR-495-3p	-0.18	MS00004347	MSY0002817	MIN0002817	THBS2
hsa-miR-506-3p	-0.20	MS00009856	MSY0002878	MIN0002878	THBS2
hsa-miR-520d-5p	-0.23	MS00033866	MSY0002855	MIN0002855	THBS2
hsa-miR-524-5p	-0.24	MS00031969	MSY0002849	MIN0002849	THBS2
hsa-miR-582-3p	-0.16	MS00010234	MSY0004797	MIN0004797	THBS2
hsa-miR-591	-0.48	MS00004907	MSY0003259	MIN0003259	THBS2
hsa-miR-598-3p	-0.28	MS00010290	MSY0003266	MIN0003266	THBS2
hsa-miR-600	-0.30	MS00004963	MSY0003268	MIN0003268	THBS1
hsa-miR-613	-0.25	MS00005054	MSY0003281	MIN0003281	THBS1
hsa-miR-618	-0.36	MS00005089	MSY0003287	MIN0003287	THBS1
hsa-miR-648	-0.31	MS00032081	MSY0003318	MIN0003318	THBS1
hsa-miR-891b	-0.39	MS00010731	MSY0004913	MIN0004913	THBS2
hsa-miR-9-5p	-0.16	MS00010752	MSY0000441	MIN0000441	THBS2
hsa-miR-922	-0.27	MS00010773	MSY0004972	MIN0004972	THBS2
hsa-miR-944	-0.29	MS00010899	MSY0004987	MIN0004987	THBS1
hsa-miR-96-5p	-0.21	MS00003360	MSY0000095	MIN0000095	THBS2
hsa-miR-98-5p	-0.24	MS00003367	MSY0000096	MIN0000096	THBS1

Transcription Factor / Histone

Test Group	Control Group	Fold Regulation Threshold	p-Value Threshold
Group 1	Control Group	2	0.05

Genes Differentially Expressed in Group 1 vs. Control Group

Position	Gene Symbol	Fold Regulation	p-Value	EpiTect ChIP qPCR Assay	Transcription Factors
D04	IL1B	3.98	0.037226	GPH1021494(-)01A	NF-AT1, TBP, NF-AT3, TFIID, c-Rel, NF-AT2, NF-AT4, RelA, NF-AT, C/EBPbeta
D05	IL6	10.3	0.005766	GPH1011803(-)01A	NF-YA, NF-AT1, NF-kappaB, NF-kappaB1, GR, c-Rel, MAZR, c-Jun, NF-AT, deltaCREB, NF-YB, Fra-1, Pax-4a, NF-kappaB2, JunB, ATF-2, CBF(2), CP1A, ATF, NF-Y, CBF-A, GR-beta, AP-1, GR-alpha, CREB, JunD, NF-E2 p45, C/EBPbeta, LCR-F1, FosB, RREB-1, NF-AT3, NF-E2, NF-AT2, NF-AT4, c-Fos, RelA, CBF-B
D06	CXCL8	2.15	0.0	GPH1010058(-)01A	C/EBPalpha
G02	THBS1	7.11	8e-06	GPH1004398(-)01A	Sp1, Tal-1beta, GR, RSRFC4, AP-2beta, Tal-1, MEF-2A, GR-alpha, AP-2alphaA, CREB, AP-2alpha, deltaCREB, ZID, AP-2gamma, Roaz, E47, c-Myb, aMEF-2, ITF-2
G03	THBS2	2.39	0.000102	GPH1025310(-)01A	FOXL1, IRF-2, TBP, RSRFC4, IRF-1, MEF-2A, Evi-1, MEF-2, aMEF-2
B06	CXCL9	-3.98	0.02228	GPH1023726(-)01A	FOXL1, CP1A, NF-YA, IRF-7A, NF-Y, HNF-3beta, CBF-A, NF-YC, FOXI1, HFH-3, CBF-C, NF-YB, CP1C, Gfi-1, CBF-B, Cdc5, CBF(2), POU6F1 (c2)
G10	VEGFA	-6.65	0.015561	GPH1011376(-)01A	PPAR-gamma2, PPAR-gamma1, Hand1, COUP, Pax-4a, HTF, C/EBPalpha, AP-1, HNF-4alpha2, PPAR-alpha, CREB, XBP-1, deltaCREB, HNF-4alpha1, E47, COUP-TF, LyF-1, COUP-TF1